

THE IMPORTANCE OF MOTIVATIONAL METHODS IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article is about how to present motivational teaching methods so that they do not become the leading aspect of learning a foreign language, but fully contribute to the formation and strengthening of the study of the material. Naturally, the question of how to organize work on mastering grammatical patterns in English lessons cannot be separated from other aspects of integrated learning: lexico-semantic, orthoepic, orthographic work, from work on the formation of communicative skills in all types*

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A foreign language learner's motivation can be influenced by many factors: social, psychological, educational, and economical. In spite of the complicated situation, teachers can still do a lot to motivate their students by being observant, understanding, informed, and tactful.

If a teacher looks at his students' performance over critically, he will never be satisfied because errors and imperfections are a sure part of learning a foreign language. However, if the teacher focuses on his students' successes, he will be surprised to find how much they are learning and how hard they are trying. There will always be things for the teacher to be proud of.

The benefits of focusing on successes and achievements are manifold. Such a focus can build rapport between teachers and students, help students develop positive self-esteem, make learning pleasant, and, finally, lead to greater effort and success. Showing appreciation of students makes it easier for students to love their teacher, and interest in the subject. Of course, praise should never be overused, or it will lose its power. The teacher should be observant and give genuine, well- deserved praise in appropriate ways, keeping in mind the cultural values of the learners.

In the science of language testing, there are two types of measurement: norm referenced and criterion-referenced. The former measures a student's performance by comparing it to the performance of other students in the group. The students are arranged along a continuum ranging from the first to the last, or from the best to the worst. The result is contrasting, ranking, and competition.

Norm-referenced evaluation is like athletic competition in that prize winners are scarce. It is even worse: language learners are always competing with the same rivals because the groups of students in classes are usually fixed. There are harmful effects for both the good and the not-so-good students. The former might become conceited or sluggish, for their victories seem to be guaranteed owing to the ability gap between them and the others. The latter students will become silent and humble, lose interest and self-confidence, and eventually give up trying. So norm-referenced evaluation can motivate neither the better students, nor the slower ones. Criterion-referenced evaluation measures a student's performance by comparing it to a defined range of knowledge or skills. The students are evaluated according to standards, not each other. In classroom teaching, objectives-referenced evaluation relates students' performance to instructional

objectives for a specific course, lesson, or task. This form of criterion-referenced evaluation has clear advantages over the norm-referenced method. It gives all students a chance to succeed as long as they are attaining the teaching objectives. In the long run, students develop positive self-esteem and confidence and the ability to accurately judge their own knowledge and skills. Objectives-referenced evaluation works well with essays. When marking an essay, a teacher does not just rank it outstanding or satisfactory in comparison with the other students' essays and give a few comments based on a general impression. Instead, the teacher judges it according to how well the student has satisfied the objective(s) of that particular assignment. If, for example, the objective is to develop a topic with supporting details, then this is the standard by which the essay will be judged. The other features of the essay would be dealt with on other occasions or as other assignments. Objectives-referenced evaluation should be an integral part of the everyday teaching process, because it evaluates teaching results by referring to instructional objectives laid down during the planning stage. A competent teacher will not only pace his teaching properly, but also frequently check whether his teaching has been effective or not. Teachers should not set unrealistic demands or judgment criteria for their students, but rather depend on objectives referencing to evaluate both their students' performance and their own teaching. If objectives are realistic and appropriate and if teaching activities are effective, most students should be able to meet the requirements, and thus experience success and achievement, despite any ability gaps within a group. In addition, objective-referenced teaching and evaluation encourage everyone to try to reach the set goals. Learning a foreign language is a long and complex task. Learners need constant encouragement, and one of the best forms of encouragement comes from a sense of achievement and success. With a keen eye for achievement, an admiring eye for efforts, and a tolerant eye for differences and individuality, a skilful teacher can manage to enable the majority of his students to enjoy learning. A shift in the way we evaluate learners can work wonders.

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